

TEACHING LANGUAGE ASPECTS TO PRE-TEENS AND ADOLESCENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article examines various aspects of language, such as phonetics, morphology and phonology for teaching two groups of learners, to be specific, pre-teens and adolescents. Moreover, article shows a clear comparison of teaching these students since different approaches and methods should be applied based on students' age and level. Challenges which are faced while preparing materials takes an indispensable role for covering in this research paper.

For language learners, particularly pre-teens (9 years old) and adolescents (17 years old) two aspects of language morphology (prepositions of place) and phonetics (voiced and voiceless "th" sound) will be covered. Although topics are the same, choosing an applicable approach for target learners is the teacher's main priority. It is obvious that picking the proper method enhances and facilitates students' ability to digest provided themes.

Teaching morphology for pre-teen learners should be followed more visually and interactively since this period learners are more exposed to a fun and playful environment. So, even it is highly likely to arouse passive students and engage them in the learning process. For teaching prepositions of place, I tend to bring objects, such as balls, boxes, toys, or any objects which are available in the classroom and are preferred by my learners. They will be placed in different locations and asked students to name the proper one to use. To illustrate this point, a ball is placed under the table and learners should name preposition "under". This way of teaching pre-teens assists to visualize the process, and achieve successful accomplishment via communicative skills. As Ybarra et al. (2008) mentioned "social interaction and relationships not only sharpen our knowledge and social skills, but also strengthen the cognitive processes that underlie those skills".

Another way to dive students deeply into the theme and convey clear explanations is by using pictures that include a wide range of objects laying around different locations, it can be a living room, bathroom, or kitchen where students get an opportunity to make simple sentences using correct prepositions. Teacher is highly centered during the process of teaching young learners. When it comes to adolescents, teaching prepositions of place can be conducted and explained in the context format by making direct examples. Flashcards can also come at hand where sentences are written with missed prepositions. Implementing

suggestopedia by listening to songs and finding prepositions of place with providing explanations about their usage and role is another way to raise their awareness. It does not mean that adolescents will be restricted from conceiving topics efficiently, due to the late starting of learning beginner-level topics. According to Collins & White (2011), “the earlier starters were not able to retain learning advantages in the longer run: all age-related differences were leveled out over the course of secondary and high school”.

Teaching phonetics is one of the hardest aspects for learners. Most learners are not able to pronounce some sounds properly which in turn leads to poor pronunciation and misunderstandings. It is quite important to start explanation with the difference between “voiced and voiceless th sound” by demonstrating videos or pictures where the tongue is placed between teeth. Students should be aware that this view represents “th” sound. As for young learners, I ask them to repeat words after me which will be written on the board. Correctly pronouncing of “voiced th” sound comes between 8-9 years. Flashcards with a wide range of words can be helpful for students to engage interactively in tasks. They should put these words in the correct row by practicing the sound several times, learners define relevant options. I raise learners’ interest by playing board games, “BINGO” and etc.

Adolescents can be taught to pronounce these sounds by watching videos of shows, programs, or some movies where “th” sound is noticeably used. Students are asked to determine where and which type of sound was used during the process. Teaching these sounds in phrases and sentences is the most appropriate approach for not only adolescents, but also older age groups. After providing clear explanations, students engage in the process by themselves, I serve as a controller, and lessons are mostly conducted in a student-centered way. “Teachers still retain power in the classroom, it is more interesting and useful to work on putting this power to good use than to imagine it can be removed” (Johnston, 1999, p. 560).

From my perspective, preparing materials and teaching materials to young learners are much more complicated and teachers’ creativity should be taken into account. The more enjoyable activities and methods, the easier to dive students into them. 9 years old age is the stage where students are mostly exposed to games and fun activities. On the contrary, for adolescents no need to prepare colorful pictures, or cards to catch their interest, better to include technology in the lesson. This period of the age is prone to social media and technological advancements which is effortless for teachers to implement into lessons. It is obvious to face advanced and lagging students, in that case, I place them together to organize mutual support. Working in pairs or in groups where the levels of students will be mixed to make a balance can ease teachers’ roles during the lesson.

Regarding challenges and benefits, teaching phonetics for “th” sound for both ages of learners requires a long-term process since it cannot be easily learned in a couple of lessons, they should get accustomed to this sound by practicing on a constant basis. Overall, all sounds in language can be improved by the regular practice where both time and effort are needed. In terms of benefits, if they learned from an early age, avoiding pronunciation might happen earlier. Krashen, Long & Scarcella (1979) conducted a survey of age relations where was revealed that “later or older starters appear to have higher results than early or young starters, especially in morphology”. Due to the fact that they will be aware of their L1 grammatical constructions, where they can easily use some prompts for learning another

language. Making sensible and true differentiation and adaptation can be a bit difficult. As there are different types of students in one class, the teacher should take into consideration all of their cognitive skills, intrinsic abilities, degree of intelligence and learning speeds. Moreover, teaching absolutely strange or unusual sounds causes teachers to face some challenges as our brain does not contain a box which is specialized in producing that sound. In terms of beneficial sides, after constant practice they can achieve their goals being able to pronounce the words correctly and avoid mistakes having native-like pronunciation. However, teaching morphological aspects to older learners is seemed to be more straightforward since it is clued by researchers mentioned above.

To sum up, picking applicable approaches for teaching any language field for different age groups is the main responsibility of teachers, adapting these methods to them is another noticeable duty. Both of them are advantageous to build successful growth in teaching learners. By analyzing findings and putting them into practice visible progress can be implemented.

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